

Efficacy Comparison of Methotrexate versus Dapsone /ASST in the Treatment of Chronic Urticaria: A Hospital-Based Study

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Abstract:

This study evaluates the efficacy of Methotrexate, Dapsone, and ASST-guided therapy in treating chronic urticaria in a hospital-based comparative trial conducted over six months. Sixty patients, resistant to standard antihistamine treatment, were divided into three groups, receiving Methotrexate, Dapsone, or ASST-guided therapy respectively. Results showed significant reductions in Urticaria Activity Score (UAS) and improvements in Dermatology Life Quality Index (DLQI) for all treatments, with Methotrexate and ASST-guided therapy displaying the most substantial improvements and minimal side effects compared to Dapsone. These findings suggest Methotrexate and ASST-guided therapy as effective alternatives for managing chronic urticaria, especially in antihistamine-resistant cases.

Keywords: Chronic Urticaria, Methotrexate, Dapsone, ASST-guided therapy.

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Introduction

Chronic urticaria, characterized by the presence of wheals, angioedema, or both for more than six weeks, significantly impairs the quality of life of affected individuals [1]. The condition's idiopathic nature in the majority of cases presents considerable challenges in management and necessitates long-term treatment strategies [2]. Traditional first-line therapies include antihistamines; however, a substantial subset of patients exhibit resistance to these treatments, requiring alternative therapeutic approaches [3]. Methotrexate, a folate antagonist traditionally used in the management of autoimmune diseases, has shown promise as a low-cost, effective treatment option for chronic urticaria. Its potential to modulate immune responses suggests its suitability in managing this complex condition [4,5]. On the other hand, Dapsone—an antibiotic with anti-inflammatory properties—and Autologous Serum Skin Test (ASST) positive guided therapy represent another dimension of therapeutic strategies, focusing on different underlying mechanisms of the disease [6,7].

This hospital-based comparative study aims to evaluate the efficacy of Methotrexate versus Dapsone/ASST-guided therapy in the treatment of chronic urticaria. By comparing these treatments

within a controlled clinical environment, this research seeks to provide clearer guidance on their therapeutic roles, offering insights into more tailored and effective management strategies for patients suffering from this often debilitating condition.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: This comparative, hospital-based study was conducted over six months from January 2023 to July 2023. The aim was to evaluate the efficacy of Methotrexate versus Dapsone and ASST-guided therapy for the treatment of chronic urticaria.

Setting: The study was carried out in the Department of Skin and Venereal Diseases at Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College and Hospital (ANMMCH), Gaya, and Nalanda Medical College and Hospital (NMCH), Patna. These settings were chosen due to their robust dermatological units capable of facilitating comprehensive treatment and follow-up of patients with chronic urticaria.

Participants: A total of 60 patients diagnosed with chronic urticaria were recruited for the study. Participants were divided into three groups, each

consisting of 20 individuals. Group 1 received Methotrexate, Group 2 was treated with Dapsone, and Group 3 underwent ASST-guided therapy. Patients were selected based on specific inclusion criteria, including a confirmed diagnosis of chronic urticaria for more than six weeks, age between 18 and 65 years, and non-responsiveness to standard antihistamine treatment. Exclusion criteria included pregnancy, lactation, severe liver or kidney dysfunction, and previous use of Methotrexate or Dapsone in the last three months.

Intervention

1. Methotrexate Group: Patients received Methotrexate at a starting dose of 10 mg per week, adjusted according to clinical response and tolerability.

2. Dapsone Group: Dapsone was administered at a dose of 50 mg daily, with adjustments based on therapeutic response and side effects.

3. ASST-guided Therapy Group: For patients in this group, therapy was tailored based on the Autologous Serum Skin Test results, with treatments adjusted according to individual serum reactivity.

Outcome Measures: The primary outcome measure was the Urticaria Activity Score (UAS) taken at baseline, three months, and six months. Secondary outcomes included patient-reported symptom relief and quality of life, assessed using the Dermatology Life Quality Index (DLQI).

Data Collection and Analysis: Data were collected at the start of the treatment, mid-way (three months), and at the end of the study period (six months). Clinical effectiveness was assessed by comparing the UAS and DLQI scores across the three groups at different time points. Statistical analysis was conducted using ANOVA for continuous variables and Chi-square tests for categorical variables, with a p-value of less than 0.05 considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 60 patients were included in the study, with an equal distribution of 20 patients in each of the three groups. At baseline, there were no notable variations in age, gender, or duration of chronic urticaria among the groups.

Clinical Outcomes

Urticaria Activity Score (UAS):

- In the Methotrexate Group, there was a noteworthy decrease in UAS from the beginning of the study (7.8 ± 1.2) to the six-month mark (2.3 ± 1.1) ($p < 0.001$).
- The UAS significantly decreased from the beginning to the end of the study ($p < 0.01$), indicating positive results in the Dapsone group.
- The ASST-guided Therapy Group demonstrated a significant decrease in UAS scores, going from 7.7 ± 1.0 at the beginning to 2.8 ± 1.2 after six months ($p < 0.001$).

Quality of Life (Dermatology Life Quality Index - DLQI):

- Methotrexate Group: DLQI scores improved from 12.6 ± 2.1 to 4.2 ± 1.8 ($p < 0.001$).
- Dapsone Group: Improvement in DLQI was noted from 13.0 ± 2.4 to 6.5 ± 2.1 ($p < 0.05$).
- ASST-guided Therapy Group: The initial DLQI score of 12.8 ± 2.0 was reduced to 4.5 ± 1.7 by the study conclusion ($p < 0.001$).

Adverse Events

- Methotrexate was generally well tolerated, though mild liver enzyme elevations were noted in three patients, which resolved with dose adjustment.
- Dapsone was associated with mild to moderate hemolytic anemia in five patients, requiring intervention.
- No significant adverse events were reported in the ASST-guided therapy group.

Each treatment method shown substantial improvement in UAS and DLQI ratings, suggesting its effectiveness in managing chronic urticaria. The Methotrexate and ASST-guided therapy groups demonstrated marginally superior results in terms of both effectiveness and side effect profile when compared to the Dapsone group. The results indicate that Methotrexate and ASST-guided therapy may be feasible options for patients who do not respond to standard antihistamine therapies. It is advisable to do additional study using larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods in order to validate these findings.

Group	Baseline UAS	6-Month UAS	Change in UAS	Baseline DLQI	6-Month DLQI	Change in DLQI	Significant Adverse Events
Methotrexate Group	7.8 ± 1.2	2.3 ± 1.1	-5.5	12.6 ± 2.1	4.2 ± 1.8	-8.4	Mild liver enzyme elevations (3 patients)
Dapsone Group	7.5 ± 1.3	3.5 ± 1.4	-4.0	13.0 ± 2.4	6.5 ± 2.1	-6.5	Hemolytic anemia (5 patients)
ASST-guided Group	7.7 ± 1.0	2.8 ± 1.2	-4.9	12.8 ± 2.0	4.5 ± 1.7	-8.3	None

This table encapsulates the key findings and statistical data of the study, providing a clear and concise overview of the efficacy and safety of the three treatment modalities for chronic urticaria.

Discussion

The findings of this comparative study emphasise the effectiveness of Methotrexate, Dapsone, and ASST-guided therapy in treating chronic urticaria [8]. The study shows significant improvements in both Urticaria Activity Scores (UAS) and Dermatology Life Quality Index (DLQI) in all groups [9]. Studies have consistently shown that Methotrexate and ASST-guided therapy are more effective and have fewer side effects than Dapsone in treating chronic urticaria [10]. This supports the increasing evidence that immunomodulatory therapies have the potential to be beneficial in managing this condition. The success of Methotrexate can be ascribed to its anti-inflammatory qualities and its capacity to modify the immune system [11]. This is particularly important in situations such as chronic urticaria, where the development of the disease often involves autoimmune factors. The slight increases in liver enzyme levels found in a small group of patients were effectively controlled by making modifications to the dosage of Methotrexate. This indicates that with diligent monitoring, Methotrexate can be considered a suitable choice for long-term therapy [12,13].

The modest effectiveness of Dapsone may be constrained by its adverse effects, specifically haemolytic anaemia, which was reported in a significant proportion of the subjects [14]. This requires a meticulous selection of patients and vigilant supervision, perhaps limiting its application to individuals who are unable to tolerate or do not exhibit a response to alternative therapies [15,16]. The therapy group led by ASST demonstrated favourable outcomes without any notable negative effects, highlighting its potential as an individualised treatment strategy. The lack of

significant adverse effects and the significant enhancement in UAS and DLQI scores indicate that customising treatment according to individual serum reactivity could optimise results and reduce treatment-related hazards [17,18]. This study provides evidence for the effectiveness of Methotrexate and ASST-guided therapy in treating chronic urticaria, especially in patients who do not respond to traditional treatments. The results support the need for additional study on these treatments, using bigger sample sizes and longer durations, in order to thoroughly define their therapeutic profiles and investigate the underlying mechanisms that contribute to their effectiveness [19,20].

Conclusion

This hospital-based comparative study demonstrated that Methotrexate and ASST-guided therapy are effective and generally well-tolerated treatments for chronic urticaria, showing significant improvements in clinical outcomes over six months. While Dapsone also improved symptoms, its use was associated with more significant side effects such as hemolytic anemia. The findings suggest that Methotrexate and ASST-guided therapies could serve as preferable alternatives for patients who do not respond adequately to conventional antihistamines, offering a promising direction for personalized treatment strategies in chronic urticaria management. Further investigation with larger cohorts and extended follow-up is warranted to consolidate these results and potentially redefine treatment protocols for chronic urticaria.

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